

Nature's Nitrogen Dream Team

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Imagine your garden or crop field is not green and plants are stunted. Surely, you will not like that. You may have thoughts about crop yields and food security or about the beauty of nature. Without nitrogen, plants remain stunted and yellowish, and harvest output from such plants is limited (Fig. 1A). Over 10,000-15,000 years of plant domestication and development of agriculture, farmers started applying natural sources of nutrients like animal manure and compost to promote plant growth. They later figured that some plants known today as legumes, such as beans, peas, soybeans, lentils, peanuts, and many more, grew well as pioneer plants in nutrient-depleted soils. Then, farmers planted legumes before, or together with, other crops to replenish nutrients in the soil. In the 1800s, the French chemist Jean-Baptiste Boussingault identified nitrogen as an important nutrient for plants and found that they cannot absorb it directly from the air. With the increase of the world's population, the demand for food surged. To mitigate this problem, Fritz Haber developed, in 1909, a method to chemically convert nitrogen gas (N_2) into ammonia. Subsequently, Carl Bosch at BASF scaled-up Haber's method to produce synthetic nitrogen-based fertilizer, which was a game changer in agriculture and food security. During the Green Revolution, farmers started to use new tools such as high-yielding, disease-resistant dwarf varieties of wheat thanks to Norman Borlaug's pioneering work in the 1940s-1960s, while chemical fertilizer use became widespread. These saved billions of people from starvation worldwide. Currently, 108 million tons (Mt) of industrial nitrogenous fertilizers are being used yearly to ensure global food security (Inorganic Fertilizers, 2024).

Farmers use nitrogenous-based fertilizer to support plant growth and yield, but plants can only utilize 61 to 65% of applied nitrogen; the rest leaches away in the environment (Sebilo et al., 2013). This inefficient manner of nitrogen usage creates

significant problems in our environment. Leached nitrogen reaches water bodies and creates dead zones where aquatic life dies. In addition, nitrogenous-based fertilizer contributes approx. 5% to greenhouse gas (GHG) emission (Gao & Serrenho, 2023).

One may ask: if 78% nitrogen is available in the atmosphere, why can't plants use it? Plants can only uptake nitrogen in the form of ammonium or nitrate. Furthermore, no plants, animals, or fungi have the functionality to break down atmospheric nitrogen. In contrast, some soil bacteria can convert atmospheric nitrogen to ammonium or nitrate because they produce nitrogenase, the only enzyme known to convert atmospheric nitrogen gas to ammonia. About 60 million years ago, a subgroup of leguminous plants, including alfalfa, beans, peas, soybeans, lupin, etc., developed a relationship with bacteria that can fix atmospheric nitrogen and are collectively called rhizobia. This is what is known as Symbiotic Nitrogen Fixation (SNF). To facilitate SNF, rhizobia must enter the host plant; thus, these legumes build little "houses" called nodules on their roots, where nitrogen-fixing bacteria enter and undergo a series of developmental processes, turning them into the nitrogen-fixing form called bacteroid. At this stage, root nodules turn pink due to the production of a legume hemoglobin (leghemoglobin), which is an oxygen carrier protecting the bacterial nitrogenase from inactivation by oxygen, and delivers enough oxygen to rhizobia to function (Fig. 1B top). Interestingly, plant leghemoglobins are similar in structure and functions to the human hemoglobin in our blood. In this mutually beneficial symbiosis, bacteria benefit from a "home" specifically constructed to maintain low oxygen levels that allow the nitrogen fixation enzyme to function. If these bacteria were to reside in other parts of the plant where oxygen levels are comparable to those in the air, nitrogen fixation would be nearly impossible. In exchange for ammonia, the host plants supply rhizobia with food in the form of sugars from photosynthesis.

Normally, one might expect that, if plants like legumes acquire fertilizer nitrogen through the symbiotic association with nitrogen-fixing bacteria, these plants would not need any more fertilizer. In reality, legume crops receive various amounts of nitrogen fertilizer to enhance yield. This is because not all nitrogen-fixing symbioses are highly and equally efficient. Farmers want high yields, and SNF is generally insufficient. However, application of synthetic nitrogen fertilizers on legume crops reduces or completely inhibits

the environmentally friendly process of symbiotic nitrogen fixation. This is such a waste, rendering nature's nitrogen dream team useless. Extensive efforts have been made in the past 25 years to understand molecular mechanisms underlying SNF and how to make this process more efficient (Roy et al., 2019). Thousands of plant and bacterial genes have been linked to SNF, and a few hundreds have been fully or partially characterized.

Figure 1: In the absence of nitrogen fertilizer, non-legume plants like corn display signs of nitrogen starvation, such as yellow-brown leaves, and produce few and small corn cobs compared to plants that received the required amount of nitrogen (Amiour et al., 2012) (A). *M. truncatula* and *Sinorhizobium* spp. form symbiotic associations leading to the development of root nodules that can be regarded as mini-factories where ammonia is produced from atmospheric nitrogen (B top). In the absence of the MtNPD1 protein, incompatible rhizobia such as Sm1021 trigger the development of small, white nodules defective in nitrogen fixation in *npd1-1* mutant plants (B bottom).

To understand more about this process and to uncover new genetic and molecular mechanisms controlling symbiotic nitrogen fixation efficiency, in our research, we use a

model plant named *Medicago truncatula* (barrel medic), which is closely related to alfalfa. This plant established symbiotic relationships with a group of *Sinorhizobium* spp. bacteria (Fig. 1B top). Pislariu et al. (2019) reported that *M. truncatula* nodule-specific Polycystin-1, Lipoxygenase, Alpha (α)-Toxin (PLAT) domain-encoding gene (*MtNPD1*) is essential for bacterial survival inside the nodule (Fig. 1B bottom). The disruption of this gene also triggers host-strain specificity. This means that, in its absence, one species of bacteria (*S. meliloti* 1021) dies, and no nitrogen fixation occurs (nodules remain small and white with no leghemoglobin), but other species of bacteria (*S. meliloti* Rm41, *S. meliloti* T073) survive and fix nitrogen. Why does this phenomenon take place? In the Pislariu lab at Texas Woman's University, we are dissecting this protein using molecular tools to solve the puzzle. Why only some rhizobia die without this protein, while others thrive? Is there a bacterial connection? We are working diligently to answer these questions.

References

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